

May 1, 2025

JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE
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UDC: 001.891

International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 10.05.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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SUT SANOATIDA QO‘LLANILADIGAN SUT KISLOTALI MIKROORGANIZMLAR TOZA KULTURASINI OLISH USHLUBLARI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi sut kislotalari bakteriyalarning fermentatsiya jarayonidagi muhimligi, ularning xillari, qo‘llanilish sohalari, toza holatda ajratib olish va uning usullari, qatlamli ekish usuli va sut kislotasi mikroorganizmlarini identifikatsiyasi uchun molekular-genetik usullarni qo‘llanilishi haqida haqida ma’lumotlar keltirilgan

Kalit so‘zlar: *Lactobacillus, Streptococcus, Lactococcus, Bifidobacterium, Leuconostoc*, gomofermentativ, geterofermentativ, liofilizatsiya, polimeraza zanjir reaksiyasi (PZR).

Kirish

Sut sanoatida sut kislotali mikroorganizmlar (SKM) mahsulotlarning fermentatsiya jarayonini boshqarishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ular nafaqat mahsulot ta’mini shakllantirish, balki uning saqlash muddatini uzaytirishda ham ishtirok etadi. SKM-larga *Lactobacillus, Streptococcus, Lactococcus, Bifidobacterium* va *Leuconostoc* jinsiga mansub bakteriyalar kiradi. Ularning toza kulturasini ajratib olinib, sanoatda qo‘llash uchun tayyorlanadi [1].

Sut sanoatida SKM-lar biologik xususiyatlariga qarab gomofermentativ va geterofermentativ bakteriyalarga bo‘linadi. Homofermentativ bakteriyalar faqat sut kislotasini hosil qilib, mahsulotlarning fermentatsiyasini nazorat qiladi (*Lactococcus lactis, Streptococcus thermophilus*). Geterofermentativ bakteriyalar esa sut kislotasidan tashqari sirka kislotasi, etanol va karbonat angidrid ham hosil qiladi (*Leuconostoc mesenteroides, Lactobacillus brevis*), bu esa pishloq va achitilgan mahsulotlarning o‘ziga xos ta’mini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega [2].

Asosiy qism

Sanoatda SKM-larni qo‘llashdan oldin ularning toza kulturasini ajratib olinadi. Toza kulturani olishning eng asosiy usuli selektiv oziqa muhitlaridan foydalanishdir. *Lactobacillus* jinsiga tegishli bakteriyalar MRS (de Man, Rogosa, Sharpe) muhitida, *Streptococcus* bakteriyalari esa M17 muhitida samarali o‘sadi. *Bifidobacterium* uchun TPY (Trypticase-Phytone-Yeast) va *Leuconostoc* uchun APT (All Purpose Tween) muhitlari ishlatiladi [3].

Mikroorganizmlar	Selektiv muhit
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<i>Lactobacillus</i>	MRS (de Man, Rogosa, Sharpe)
<i>Streptococcus</i>	M17 muhiti
<i>Bifidobacterium</i>	TPY (Trypticase-Phytone-Yeast) muhiti
<i>Leuconostoc</i>	APT (All Purpose Tween) muhiti

Laboratoriyalarda qatlamli ekish usuli keng qo'llaniladi. Bunda mikroorganizmlar steril plastinka yoki Petri idishiga ekilib, sekin-asta suyultirish orqali toza koloniyalar ajratib olinadi. Shuningdek, mikrobiologik filtrlash va tsentrifugatsiya usullari ham qo'llaniladi. 0,22-0,45 mikronlik filtrlar yordamida bakteriyalar kontaminatsiyadan tozalanadi, 5000-10000 rpm tezlikda tsentrifugatsiya qilinganda esa bakteriyalar cho'kmaga tushadi [4].

Zamonaviy mikrobiologiyada SKM-larning aniq identifikatsiyasi uchun molekulyar-genetik usullar qo'llaniladi. Polimeraza zanjir reaksiyasi (PZR) orqali bakteriyalarning 16S rRNA geni tahlil qilinib, ularning aniq turi aniqlanadi. Bundan tashqari, DNK-sekvenirlash usuli bakteriyalarning genomik darajada tekshirilishini ta'minlaydi. Bu texnologiyalar nafaqat aniq tashxis qo'yish, balki genetik modifikatsiyalangan shtammlarni yaratishda ham muhim ahamiyatga ega [1].

Olingan toza kulturani uzoq muddat saqlash uchun turli usullar qo'llaniladi. Liofilizatsiya (quritish usuli) mikroorganizmlarni vakuum va past harorat yordamida quritib, ularning hayotiylikini 10-15 yilgacha saqlash imkonini beradi. Suyuq azotda saqlash (-196°C) bakteriyalarni 20-30 yil davomida saqlashga imkon beradi. Muzlatish usuli (-80°C) esa 10-20% glitserin eritmasida bakteriyalarni saqlashga yordam beradi [2].

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, sut sanoatida qo'llaniladigan SKM-lar mahsulot sifatini va saqlash muddatini yaxshilash uchun keng qo'llaniladi. Ularning toza kulturasi selektiv muhitlar, qatlamli ekish, mikrobiologik filtrlash va molekulyar-genetik usullar orqali ajratib olinadi. Zamonaviy saqlash texnologiyalari esa ushbu mikroorganizmlarning uzoq muddat davomida samaradorligini ta'minlaydi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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